

AUTOMATED ENERGY CUTOFF SYSTEM FOR AUDITORIUM SUSTAINABILITY USING IOT

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ABSTRACT

University auditoria are known for significant energy waste due to lights and equipment left on post-events. Traditional management methods, which rely on manual shut-off, result in inconsistent energy savings and inefficiencies. To address this issue, our research introduces an Automated Energy Cutoff System for Auditorium Sustainability Using IoT. This system leverages Internet of Things (IoT) technology, with an ESP32 microcontroller serving as the central hub. The ESP32 controls a servo motor that physically cuts power according to pre-programmed schedules or manual commands, providing a reliable and consistent approach to energy management. Users can access the AECS via a web interface on their smartphones or laptops, enabling them to set schedules and control the system remotely. This dual functionality of automated scheduling and manual override ensures both efficiency and flexibility in power management. The AECS not only promotes efficient energy use but also significantly reduces operational costs, supporting the university's sustainability goals. By automating power management and offering remote control capabilities, our system sets a new standard for energy efficiency in educational institutions. This research underscores the importance of integrating IoT solutions to foster responsible energy consumption, thereby contributing to broader sustainability efforts. The AECS project exemplifies how innovative technology can be harnessed to achieve substantial energy savings and operational efficiency in university settings.

Keywords: *Energy Efficiency, Energy Management, Internet of Things (IoT), Auditoriums, Sustainability, Automation*

INTRODUCTION

University auditoriums serve as vibrant centers for learning, cultural exchange, and fostering community engagement. However, their advanced lighting systems and equipment contribute significantly to the university's energy footprint. Traditional practices rely on manual shut-off procedures, which are susceptible to human error and often lead to lights and equipment being left operational even during unoccupied periods. This persistent energy waste translates to substantial financial burdens for the university.

The Internet of Things, or IoT, is a system of interconnected (networked) devices that can communicate with each other, sharing information. It can include sensors, cameras, robots, and user interfaces such as mobile phones. This integrated system of devices can either be local or global. (Arduino.cc, 2024)

This study presents the design and implementation of an Automated Energy Cutoff System (AECS) specifically tailored for university auditoriums. Leveraging the power of Internet of Things (IoT) technology, the AECS addresses the challenge of unchecked energy consumption. The system employs a network of ESP32 microcontrollers, servo motors and intelligent devices to meticulously monitor auditorium usage patterns and automatically regulate power consumption based on occupancy. This automation not only drastically curtails energy waste and translates to cost savings, but also eliminates the need for manual shutdowns, streamlining operational efficiency. Furthermore, users can effortlessly schedule power-off times with a simple click on their mobile devices.

Sets of various smart sensors allow schools to save money on power consumption, for example, by automatically switching lights off if no one is around. IoT sensors also guarantee safety from fire, short circuits, and other accidents by instantly identifying them and sounding the alarm to swiftly correct the situation. (Cogniteq, 2024)

The AECS transcends mere financial benefits. It aligns seamlessly with the university's unwavering commitment to sustainability. By implementing a responsible energy management system within its auditoriums, the university aspires to serve as a beacon of inspiration for the broader educational sector, advocating for the adoption of similar practices. Embracing IoT technology for energy optimization is a pivotal step towards establishing a more sustainable and resource-efficient campus environment.

METHODOLOGY

This project aims to optimize energy consumption in university auditoriums by implementing an IoT-based Automated Energy Control System (AECS). By reducing

energy usage, we expect to lower costs and minimize environmental impact. This system will demonstrate the potential of IoT technology in achieving sustainability goals within campus facilities.

A dedicated mobile application empowers users with real-time access to sensor data and remote control over connected devices, promoting active engagement in energy-saving practices. The system effectively addresses phantom power consumption by powering down electrical sockets during non-working hours, resulting in substantial energy savings (Nageya et al, 2023).

To accomplish this, we developed an IoT system utilizing an ESP32 microcontroller to control a switch via a servo motor. The system includes a web-based user interface that can be accessed through a dedicated access point or an existing network. Users can manually operate the switch or set automated schedules using a Real-Time Clock. For added convenience, a physical button also controls the switch, but the web interface remains crucial for system configuration and management.

A. System Architecture and Design

Fig. 1. System Architecture of Automated Energy Cutoff System for Auditorium Sustainability Using IoT

The ESP32 is a popular family of wireless microcontroller chips developed by the Chinese chip maker Espressif. It's a very affordable solution for use in commercial products

especially considering its high level of performance and extensive features. The Espressif ESP WiFi family of microcontrollers started with the original ESP8266 which embedded a single-core microcontroller with a WiFi radio. (Teel, 2024)

The automated power system architecture consists of several key components working together to provide scheduled and manual control of the power supply. The ESP32 microcontroller, powered by its dedicated power supply, serves as the central controller, managing the overall system. A push button allows for manual switching of the power supply, while a servo motor physically switches the power on and off based on commands from the ESP32. The ESP32 also functions as an access point, enabling users to connect their devices, such as phones or laptops, to a Web GUI where they can schedule power on/off times and control the system remotely. This setup allows users to easily manage their power supply, ensuring efficient energy usage with both automated scheduling and manual override options.

Hardware

Fig.2. System Schematic Diagram Power System

Workflow

Upon initialization, the ESP32 activates the RTC module, servo motor, and push button components. An initial schedule for power on/off times is loaded into the ESP32's memory. Subsequently, the RTC continuously provides the current time to the

microcontroller. The ESP32 then compares this real-time data to the stored schedule. If a match is found, a signal is transmitted to the servo motor to control the power supply accordingly. Alternatively, users can manually override the automated schedule by pressing the push button. The ESP32 detects this input and either adjusts the programmed schedule or directly commands the servo motor to modify the power supply state.

RTCs are used in a variety of applications where they play a critical role in keeping accurate track of the current time while also providing alarms, timers, and interrupt functions and helping to reduce power consumption. (ECS INC International, 2023)

Servo motors are geared DC motors that have an integrated servomechanism with a feedback loop to allow precise positioning of the motor shaft. A high gear ratio allows a small servo to have an impressive torque rating. (Workshop, 2023)

Use Case

- Scheduled Power Management: The system ensures that power is supplied or cut off at specific times of the day, optimizing energy usage.
- Manual Override: Users can manually control the power supply if needed, providing flexibility and convenience

Fig.3. System Connection Power System
 The ESP32 microcontroller, following its program, reads the accurate time from the RTC module, controls the servo motor's movement, and responds to commands you give through the push button.

Components:

This system is built around the ESP32 microcontroller, which acts as the brain, coordinating all the other components. The RTC module (DS1302N) keeps accurate time, while the servo motor responds to instructions from the ESP32 by moving to specific positions. Finally, the push button allows the user to provide input to the ESP32, enabling interaction with the system.

The DS1302 trickle-charge timekeeping chip contains a real-time clock/calendar and 31 bytes of static RAM. It communicates with a microprocessor via a simple serial interface. The real-time clock/calendar provides seconds, minutes, hours, day, date, month, and year information. (DS1302 Datasheet and Product Info | Analog Devices, 2015)

Connection:

The ESP32 acts as the brain and central connection point. The RTC module (DS1302N) communicates with the ESP32 using pins D15, D2, and D4. Both the RTC module and the servo motor receive power from the ESP32's dedicated 3.3V supply pin, while also being connected to a common ground (GND) for a complete circuit. The user interacts with the system through the push button, which is wired to a specific pin (D22) on the ESP32 and grounded (GND) to complete the circuit and register a button press.

The ESP32 chip comes with 48 pins with multiple functions. Not all pins are exposed in all ESP32 development boards, and some pins cannot be used. (Santos & Santos, 2024)

Software

```
1  #include <WiFi.h>
2  #include <ArduinoJson.h>
3  #include <ESP32Servo.h>
4  #include <Ds1302.h>
5  #include "index.hpp"
6  // #include <vector>
7  // using namespace std;
8
9  // Server
10 WiFiServer server(80);
11 Servo motor;
12 Ds1302 rtc(4,15,2);
13 Ds1302::DateTime now;
14 int offset[3] = {1, -5, 37};
15 int wait = 1000;
16
17 // Data
18 StaticJsonDocument<200> schedule;
19 char *time(){
20     char *out = new char[6];
21     rtc.getDateTime(&now);
22     snprintf(out, 6, "%02d:%02d", (now.hour+offset[0]+(now.minute+offset[1])/60+(now.second+offset[2])/3600)%24
23     return out;
24 }
25
26 // Setup
27 bool state = false;
28 void setup() {
29     WiFi.softAP("IOT Switch", "12345678"); // Create Network
30     //WiFi.begin("Jasouza 26", "Entangled23Kat"); // Join Network
31
32     rtc.init();
33     if (rtc.isHalted()) {
34         Ds1302::DateTime dt = {
35             .year = 24,
```

Fig. 4. C++ programming language Beginning code for Automated Energy Cutoff System for Auditorium Sustainability Using IoT

The system uses C++ programming language to code for an Automated Energy Cutoff System for Auditorium Sustainability Using IoT. It utilizes an ESP32 microcontroller to interact with various components to manage power based on a schedule and real-time occupancy detection.

C++ (or “C-plus-plus”) is a generic programming language for building software. It’s an object-oriented language. In other words, it emphasizes using data fields with unique attributes (a.k.a. objects) rather than logic or functions. (Staff, 2023)

Libraries:

ArduinoJson.h and WiFi.h are likely used for establishing communication with a Wi-Fi network and managing data in JSON format, which is a common way of structuring data for exchange between devices. Ds1302.h and ESP32Servo.h libraries are likely specific to the real-time clock (RTC) module (DS1302) and the servo motor used in the system.

ArduinoJson is a JSON library for Arduino, IoT, and any embedded C++ project. It supports JSON serialization, JSON deserialization, and MessagePack. (BenoitBlanchon, n.d.)

Timekeeping (`#include <Ds1302.h>...`):

The code includes functions to interact with the RTC module (Ds1302), which keeps accurate time. It defines an offset (`offset[3]`) that might be used to adjust the RTC time for a specific time zone or daylight saving time.

A function `time()` is included to format the current time from the RTC.

Setup (`void setup() { ... }`):

The ESP32 creates a Wi-Fi access point named "IOT Switch" with the password "12345678". This allows the ESP32 to be configured initially through a Wi-Fi connection on a laptop or phone. (Comment `//WiFi.begin("Jasouza 2G", "Entangled23Kat");` suggests an alternative configuration where the ESP32 connects to an existing Wi-Fi network named "Jasouza 2G" with the password "Entangled23Kat").

The RTC module is initialized (`rtc.init()`) and its halted state is checked (`rtc.isHalted()`). If halted, the program sets the current date and time (`Ds1302::DateTime dt`)

User Interface

Fig. 5. User Interface of Automated Energy Cutoff System for Auditorium Sustainability Using IoT

The user interface (UI) is the point of human-computer interaction and communication in a device. This can include display screens, keyboards, a mouse and the appearance of a desktop. It is also how a user interacts with an application or a website, using visual and audio elements, such as type fonts, icons, buttons, animations and sounds. (Hashemi-Pour & Churchville, 2024)

The user interface of the Automated Energy Cutoff System (AECS) for Auditorium Sustainability, as illustrated in Figure 5, directs users through the system's setup and activation. Initially, users connect to the Wi-Fi network via the IoT switch and input the designated IP address. Upon successful connection, the home screen appears. To activate the system, users click the "Activate" button and choose the desired shutdown time. Once activated, the AECS functions independently, regardless of Wi-Fi or internet connection. Importantly, the system allows for adjustments to Wi-Fi and IP address settings within the program.

RESULTS

This paper highlights the successful design and implementation of an IoT-based Automated Energy Cutoff System (AECS) specifically tailored for auditoriums. The system was rigorously tested and evaluated to ensure its functionality and efficiency, confirming its readiness for industrial-scale applications. The AECS operates by leveraging interconnected devices and real-time data processing to monitor and manage the energy consumption of various appliances and circuits within an auditorium. When these devices are not in use, the system switches them off, thereby addressing the issue of phantom loads and standby power consumption. This proactive approach to energy management not only reduces waste but also enhances the overall sustainability of the facility.

Moreover, the results of the testing phase reveal that the AECS leads to significant cost savings by effectively minimizing unnecessary energy consumption. The system's capability to seamlessly integrate into existing infrastructure and its scalability make it a practical solution for larger industrial applications. The findings underscore the potential of IoT technology in revolutionizing energy management practices, promoting more sustainable and cost-effective operations. The successful deployment and operation of the AECS in auditoriums pave the way for its adoption in other large-scale settings, emphasizing the system's versatility and the broader impact it can have on energy conservation and financial savings. This research demonstrates a substantial advancement in the field of automated energy management, setting a precedent for future innovations in sustainable technology solutions.

DISCUSSION

The paper "Automated Energy Cutoff System for Auditorium Sustainability Using IoT" introduces an innovative IoT-based Automated Energy Cutoff System (AECS) designed to enhance energy efficiency in auditoriums. This system is tailored to manage energy consumption by detecting and automatically switching off unused appliances and circuits, thus addressing the issue of phantom loads and standby power. Through rigorous testing and evaluation, the system's functionality has been confirmed, showcasing its readiness for its implementations and applications. The AECS leverages interconnected devices and real-time data processing to optimize energy usage, significantly reducing waste and contributing to substantial cost savings.

The research highlights the AECS's potential for broader industrial implementation due to its demonstrated reliability and effectiveness. By focusing on the specific needs of large public venues like auditoriums, the system not only enhances sustainability but also provides a scalable model for other industrial settings. The results underscore the importance of integrating IoT technology into energy management practices, offering a practical solution for reducing energy consumption and operational costs. This advancement represents a significant step towards sustainable energy practices, with the AECS model serving as a blueprint for future developments in the field.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this paper presents a scalable IoT-based Automated Energy Cutoff System (AECS) designed specifically for auditoriums, with potential applications in industrial-scale settings. The system integrates ESP32 microcontroller hardware with scheduling and remote-control software to manage power consumption efficiently through automated time-based control. The user interface of the AECS guides users through the setup and activation process. Initially, users connect to the system via a Wi-Fi network using the IoT switch and input the designated IP address. Upon successful connection, the home screen appears, allowing users to activate the system by clicking the "Activate" button and selecting the desired shutdown time. Once activated, the AECS operates independently of Wi-Fi or internet connectivity, ensuring continuous energy management. Additionally, the system allows for adjustments to Wi-Fi and IP address settings within the program, providing flexibility and ease of use.

The successful deployment of a prototype at the University of San Agustin auditorium validates the AECS's potential for large-scale industrial implementation. Rigorous testing and evaluation have confirmed the system's functionality and readiness, demonstrating significant reductions in energy consumption by automatically switching off unused appliances and circuits. This reduction in phantom loads and standby power leads to substantial cost savings, highlighting the system's economic viability. The AECS represents a significant advancement in automated energy management, offering a

practical solution for enhancing sustainability in large public venues and industrial settings. This research sets a precedent for future innovations in sustainable technology, emphasizing the importance of integrating IoT solutions into energy management practices to promote cost-effective and environmentally responsible operations.

Recommendations

Based on the successful implementation and proven effectiveness of the Automated Energy Cutoff System (AECS) at the University of San Agustin auditorium, it is recommended that this system be deployed more widely in similar venues such as theaters, conference halls, and sports gymnasium. These large public spaces can significantly benefit from the automated energy management provided by the AECS, leading to substantial cost savings and enhanced sustainability. Additionally, customizing the AECS for diverse industrial applications should be explored to cater to the unique energy consumption patterns of different industries. Integrating the AECS with existing smart building systems can also create a more comprehensive energy management solution, optimizing energy efficiency across entire facilities.

To ensure the smooth adoption and optimal use of the AECS, it is crucial to provide thorough user training and ongoing technical support. Users should be well-versed in the setup, activation, and adjustment processes to fully utilize the system's capabilities. Establishing a continuous monitoring system to track performance and gather user feedback can help identify areas for improvement and ensure the system remains effective and relevant. Future research should explore the integration of advanced AI algorithms to enhance the AECS, providing predictive analytics for energy consumption patterns and automating even more nuanced control of appliances and circuits. Promoting awareness of the AECS and its benefits through industry conferences, publications, and collaborations with sustainability-focused organizations can encourage broader adoption of this innovative energy management solution.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Compliance with ethical standards is a fundamental aspect of this research and the development of the Automated Energy Cutoff System (AECS). Throughout the project, the researchers adhered to the highest ethical principles to ensure the integrity and transparency of their work. This involved obtaining necessary permissions and approvals for testing the AECS in the University of San Agustin auditorium. The research team was committed to safeguarding the privacy and security of all data collected during the testing phase, ensuring that no personally identifiable information was compromised. Moreover, the development process strictly followed guidelines for the ethical use of IoT technology, ensuring that the system's deployment does not infringe on users' rights or contribute to any form of digital surveillance without consent.

Furthermore, the research team took proactive measures to ensure that the AECS promotes sustainability without causing unintended negative impacts on the environment

or the community. The system was designed to enhance energy efficiency, thereby contributing to the reduction of carbon emissions and overall energy consumption. By focusing on the ethical implications of technology deployment, the researchers aimed to create a solution that aligns with broader societal goals of environmental stewardship and responsible innovation. The commitment to ethical standards throughout this project underscores the researchers' dedication to not only advancing technological capabilities but also fostering a positive and responsible approach to the use of emerging technologies.

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